

A Study of Astrology from Philosophical and Myanmar Cultural Perspective

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Abstract

Astrology is pervading in Myanmar Culture since *Bagan* Period. The definite historical document is “The earliest horoscope written on wall-painting of *kuthathamuti* pagoda of *Phwa Saw, Bagan* in 627-637 A.D”. This paper attempts to show the problem why Myanmar are so interested in astrology. The tentative solution is that the astrology gives the devotees for their satisfaction. The method is descriptive and the principle is theory of truth. This paper will contribute to differentiate what the nature of reality and human’s prediction about future in social life.

Key words: Astrology, mental satisfaction, theory of truth

Introduction

Everybody has a desire to know the consequences of his actions after he has done some kinds of deed. That impulse makes some people to check their fortune. If some kinds of obstacle or hindrance are found in his check men attempt again to find a way out or help to overcome. It may say that it is human nature in general though touch-minded persons and materialists do not believe in it. Astrology, horoscope, palmistry, etc. are the technologies which give prediction about the men’s future fortune.

“Astrology is the study of influence of stars and planets on each individual and it has a major role in shaping personality along with their future. Astrology aids the innate power to design the destiny by merging ancient wisdom with practical living. It is the five thousand- year old study of the influential effects of the sun, moon, stars, and planets on events on the earth and horoscopes are predictions or insights into our lives, made by studying the stars in our sign on the zodiac.”

The origin of astrology reflects the understanding and experience of ancient spiritual teachers regarding the facts of life. The latest discovery in astrology can correlate the patterns of the solar system with the patterns of our lives which impact us from moment to moment. There are patterns of growth and patterns of potential in the revolution of each individual life circles and various stages

In India, Vedic astrology has been described in details and Hinduism maintained it as worthy, honourable and admirable one. It is regarded as the valuable experiences and records of the ancient seers. Vedic astrology is an integral part of Indian culture and has been practiced variously.

Both eastern and western astrology are based on a predictive system. It is similar to the subject used by meteorology. The Egypt’s were the early people to follow the Babylonian principles of astrology as early as the 1ST century BC soon after it was conquered by Alexander. The Greeks started following the Babylonian astrology during the mid-4th century BC. As Egyptians were already following the Babylonian astrology it soon got merged with the Babylonian and resulted in the finding of horoscopic astrology which was very quickly followed in different other parts of the world like Europe, the Middle East as well as India.

In Myanmar, the exact documentary root of astrology was found in 627-637 A.D. at the wall painting of *Kuthathamuti* pagoda of *Phwa Saw, Bagan* though there may have been many unrecorded documents before it. Thus, one thing that is certain is that belief in astrology has an impact on Myanmar Culture like other cultures of Asia, India, China, Greece and Europe. Different forms of horoscope of Myanmar, described in the appendix of this paper are to be found in *Bagan* and other places. Myanmar’s designs of horoscope are found mixed with religious elements, such as images of Buddha

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and other spiritual beings. Most Myanmar horoscopes are designed on the palm leaves since there had been no advanced printing.

In Myanmar Culture like, astrologers predict the fortune of the devotees by calculating and reasoning a person's fortune based on his age, birth place, and his position of the planet.

As astrology has been accepted by many cultures since the ancient times though sciences and technologies have been developed, we, thus, should study its wonderful characteristics and the attitudes of the scholars on it.

Scientists and most philosophers refuse to accept the impact of astrology. For example, Karl Popper regarded it as a pseudoscience by measuring it with his falsification method. Other philosophers also assumed it unscientific and confirmed that astrology cannot be verified and validated by anyway.

Again, when astrology is measured by philosophical theories of truth, it cannot be accepted by both correspondence theory or coherences theory except the pragmatic theory.

However, since astrology gives the devotees psychological satisfaction the belief in it has been smoldering since the ancient time to the present.

Meaning of Astrology, its origin and development

Astrology is the study of movements and relative positions of celestial objects as a means for divining information about human affairs and terrestrial events.

Astrology has dated to at least the 2nd millennium BCE, and has its roots in calendrical systems used to predict seasonal shifts and to interpret celestial cycles as signs of divine communications.

Western astrology, one of the oldest astrological systems still in use, can trace its root to 19th-17th century BCE Mesopotamia, from which it spread to Ancient Greece, Rome, the Arab world and eventually Central and Western Europe.

Many cultures have attached importance to astronomical events, and some – such as the Indians and Chinese – developed elaborate systems for predicting terrestrial events from celestial observations.

Contemporary Western astrology is often associated with systems of horoscopes that purport to explain aspects of a person's personality and predict significant events in their lives based on the positions of celestial objects; the majority of professional astrologers rely on such systems.

Throughout its history, astrology was considered a scholarly tradition and was common in academic circles, often in close relation with astronomy, alchemy, meteorology, and medicine.

It was present in political circles, and is mentioned in various works of literature, from Dante Alighieri and Geoffrey Chaucer to William Shakespeare, Lope de Vega and Calderon de la Barca.

With the onset of the scientific revolution astrology was called into question. It has been challenged successfully both on theoretical and experimental grounds, and has been shown to have no scientific validity or explanatory power.

Astrology thus lost its academic and theoretical standing, and common belief in it has largely declined. Astrology is now recognized to be pseudoscience.

The scientific community rejects astrology as having no explanatory power for describing the universe, and consider it a pseudoscience. Scientific testing of astrology has been conducted, and no evidence has been found to support any of the premises or purported effects outlined in astrological traditions. There is no proposed mechanism of action by which the positions and motions of stars and planets could affect people and events on earth that does not contradict well understood, basic aspects of biology and physics. Those who continue to have faith in astrology have been characterized as doing so" In spite of the fact that there is no verified scientific basis for their beliefs, there is strong evidence to the contrary".

It has also been shown that confirmation bias is a psychological factor that contributes to belief in astrology. Confirmation bias is a form of cognitive bias. According to available literature, astrology believers tend to selectively remember predictions that turn out to be true, and do not remember those

that turn out false. Another, separate, form of confirmation bias also plays a role, where believers often fail to distinguish between messages that demonstrate special ability and those that do not. Thus, there are two distinct forms of confirmation bias that are under study with respect to astrological belief.

The Root of Astrology in Myanmar Culture

To study astrology, we must learn *nekkhats*, stars, planet and *tayar*.

Planet is a celestial body moving around the sun in an orbit. Generally an object which is stable and twinkling is called “star”, and the object which is moving and its brightness is stable, it is called “planet”. In Myanmar’s astrology, term ‘planet’ (ဂြိုဟ်) means “abode” (ဗိမာန်) There are nine planets including earth planet which are rotating around the sun. In Myanmar astrology, the sun represents to Sunday, Moon represents Monday and the rest, Mercury, Jupiter, Venus, Saturn, refers to Tuesday, Wednesday, Thursday, Friday and Saturday in order. There are two other more planets namely, *Rahu* (ရာဟု) and *Ketu*(udwf). In Fact, *Rahu* and *Ketu* do not involve in orbiting of planet but they are just accepted as planets by the view of Myanmar astrology.

We acknowledge that comet (*Nekkhat*) means a kind of formation by the group of stars. But, *Taya* means a kind of class or group of stars which are formed in imaginary the nearer star which are scattering in the space or they are slathered stars in the sky, making an imaginary line through the closer stars, we make various names. There is no difference between nekkhat and taya, and we use them in turn as we wish. In Myanmar astrology, ‘taya’ is a grump of 9 main stars which parallel to the 27 lunar mansions (nekkhat).

(1) Asvini Nekkhat

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|---------------------------|------------------------------|
| (1) Crow Mansion | (2) Bharani Nekkhat |
| | (3) Krittika Nekkhat |
| | (4) Rohini Nekkhat |
| (2) Brahminy duck mansion | (5) Mrigasiras nekkhat |
| | (6) Ardra |
| | (7) Punarvarn Nekkhat |
| (3) Prawn Mansion | (8) Pushya Nekkhat |
| | (9) Aslesha Nekkhat |
| | (10) Magha Nekkhat |
| (4) Seale mansion | (11) Purva Phalguni Nekkhat |
| | (12) Uttara Phalguni Nekkhat |
| | (13) Hasta Nekkhat |
| (5) Mansion | (14) Chitra Nekkhat |
| | (15) Svati Nekkhat |
| | (16) Visakha Nekkhat |
| (6) Fishing mansion | (17) Anuradha Nekkhat |
| | (18) Jyeshtha Nekkhat |
| | (19) Mula Nekkhat |
| (7) Elephant mansion | (20) Purva Ashadha Nekkhat |
| | (21) Uttara Ashadha Nekkhat |
| | (22) Sravana Nekkhat |

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|-----------------------|-------------------------|
| (8) Horse taya | (23) Dhanishtha Nekkhat |
| | (24) Satataraka Nekkhat |
| | (25) Purva Bhadrapada |
| (9) Little egret taya | (26) Uttara Bhadrapada |
| | (27) Revati Bhadrapada |

For Notification:

Saing taya (□□□□□□□□) is called Abizi nekkhat (□□□□□□□□) and if we count including them there are 28 nekkhats in total.

Since ancient time, almost in all cultures of the world, men have believed that they could predict the men's fortune by calculating the relation of nature, position and movement of the planets, stars, nekkhats and tayas and men's present positions.

For aspects of culture in every nationality, it's been a long time that people believed the astrology that can tell their fortune. The nine planets inching the earth rotate the sun from their existence in elliptical exhibit. Rotating from the sun's equator line, orbits are all straight. Far away from the sun, moon and the planets, there is a zodiac which is comprised of stars, tayas and it has 12 zodiacal signs made up of stars.

Based on them, the astrologers make a horoscope of person by according depending on this birthdates. With the help of horoscope, the astrology is started to forecast the fortune of a person's future, typically including a delineation of character and circumstances, biased on the relative proportions of the stars and planets from Zanama, Pattika, Zanama means birth and Pattika means making a note related to that birth.

According to the record, the earliest horoscope is created for the Nwal Pat Township, Yaw Naka Region in Myanmar. In that horoscope, Aquarius has Sunday and Wednesday, Saturn; Friday, Rahu were in Pisces, Monday and Tuesday implied Leo; Thursday was in Libra. As now, in Buddhist era (2539) years that Nwal Pat Township has existed for (2439) years. Myanmar horoscope come from Central India and people used it widely after Srihittra.

From Bagan Dynasty to Invar Dynasty people draw mural horoscope and we can see them up to now. In Nyaung Yam Dynasty and Konbaung Dynasty, People recorded and wrote horoscopes and astrology on materials palm leaf inscription, palm leaf horoscope, ceiling horoscope, Palmyra leaf, gold horoscope, elephant tusk horoscope, bamboo horoscope, stone horoscope. And there were so many kinds of horoscopes; birthdate horoscope, wedding horoscope, plaque of the coronation horoscope, pagoda building horoscope, bringing Pitale ceremony horoscope, establishing capitals and villages horoscope. People wrote those horoscopes with numbers in that above materials designed with Myanmar floral arts. They are:

1. The earliest mural horoscopes were Buddhist zodiacal circles made in Myanmar Era (627-637). They were 5 horoscopes on the ceiling of Tikema Akuu in the Kusasmuti Pagoda pavilion near the Phwar Saw village, Bagan, donated by the King Nara Thiha Patae's grandma called 'Phwar Saw'. Ceiling horoscope (Example) Senath ceiling of the west pavilion the Gubyaukng Temple, Myingaba village, Bagan in A.D 650.
2. Example 2: mural horoscope in the north ceiling of the west pavilion in the north of Myingaba, Bagan in A.D 672.
3. Examples horoscope in A.D 725 at the east ceiling of the south relic chamber of the Gubyaukng Temple in north Myingaba village, Bagan.
4. Example 4, 15 horoscopes in the Phaya Thone Zu in Min Nan Thu village, Bagan.

5. Example 5, horoscope of in AD 812 in PhayaThone Zu in Min Nan Thu village, Bagan.
6. Example 6, horoscopes in AD 907 of the east ceiling in the north of the Mon Eave in the west Taung Bi village, Bagan.
7. Example (7), in AD 937, horoscope of the Center pole in Mon caves in the west Taung Bi village, Bagan.
8. Example (8), in AD 1029, horoscope in the south entrance ceiling of the relic chamber No. 1307 Cave next to the north of Mon Cave Taung Bi, Bagan.

Thus, we should accept those vivid features of the map of Myanmar astrology.

The European astrology also believes that the phenomena of the movement of the sun, moon, planet, stars can be powerful over human's fortune and can create the change. Example, Jupiter and stern meet in a zodiac for every 20th year. People supposed that the US presidents who are elected in such year is assassinated or die in other ways.

- (1) The US president William Henry Harrison who was elected in 1840 when Jupiter and Saturn met in Capricorn died of pneumonia in his 31st day in his office.
- (2) The US president, Abraham Lincoln who wins the election in 1860 when Jupiter and Saturn were in Virgo was assassinated while serving as president for a second term.
- (3) The president James A. Garfield who led US in 1880 when Jupiter and Saturn were together in Taurus was assassinated.
- (4) The US president William McKinley who was elected in 1900 when Jupiter and Saturn in Capricorn was assassinated in 1901.
- (5) The president Warren G. Harding who ruled the country in 1920 when Jupiter and Saturn were in Virgo died in 1923 while serving as president.
- (6) The Franklin D. Roosevelt won the reelection in 1940 when Jupiter and Saturn were in Taurus died in his third term.
- (7) The president Kennedy who was elected in 1960 when Jupiter and Saturn met in Capricorn was assassinated in 1963.
- (8) The US president Reagan who led US in 1980 when Jupiter and Saturn were together in Virgo was assassinated in March 30, 1981. But luckily with an exception, the president did not die luckily.

Astrology is so deep and it has wide range to learn. Astrology did not come into Myanmar in a sudden movement but it proceeded and developed gradually. It devolved and evolved. But it stood against the difficulties. At last it still alive now. Astrology is the study of good omen and bad omen appeared in the earth and the space, the good and bad sign of elephant taya, falling stars, cloud glowing with reflected light an eclipse of the sun and the moon. And astrologic forecast people's fortune based on them.

Astrology derived from Hindu Brahminism. On the fullmoonday of Kason (Friday) in Myanmar Era 68, Queen Maya Devi gave birth to prince Siddhartha, Buddha to be, amongst a grove of Sal trees in Lumbini (Kathmandu Town, Nepal). Rising their two fingers each, Raja, Daza, Lekhana, Jordimanda, Ya Nya, Subawwa, Suyama, Brahmins, foretold that the prince would be the Universal Monarch or lord Buddha. Sudahatha, a young Brahmin, presented, rising one finger, that the prince would be the incomparable lord Buddha beyond any doubt. Astronomy had existed long before and Sama, Yaza, Kura, Ahtavanda Hindu Religious works, the Vedas (Vedic) Astrology, was very dominant and influential at that time. In many Treatises of the Shastra, being tactful in Auspicious or Ominous saying, Prophecies, Oracles, Essence, Omens, Plats and futures, which have been extracted from the works of Sama, there are Asa Shastra, Clarifying the significant and idiosyncratic signs and habits of horse. Similarly, Gaza Shastra for elephant, Triyasona Shastra for animals, Mani Shastra for Gems and Jewels Keihti Shastra for Women, Purisa Shastra for Men and Samudika Shastra. Those Shastras are used for being perceptive in classifying and analyzing the signs and habits of human beings as well as animals, and they are also called physiognomy (studying the appearances). There is not exact

information when the astrology was started. But we can estimate it due to the fact that there was a prohibition to monks “not to tell physiognomist, not to tell astrology” since the beginning of the Buddhist Era. That is why it is sure that astrology had already known before Buddhist Era.

In the literature of Aryan Race in Indus Delta Region, astrology, traditional medicine, alchemy, cabalistic square were famous. Hindus valued them as the precious literature. From there, it spreader Easter countries including Myanmar and it combined with their oriental customs. Thus it is difficult for us to trace where it was started first.

Among those earliest theses, Thurira Theindan Ta Thesis, one of the treatises on Hindu astrology is up to date and popular still. Hindu Puran thesis and Rid Waida thesis were written since 5000 or 6000 years ago. Sandara belief came into the upper Myanmar from northern India and combined with Buddhism as Sandara Buddhism. That’s the fact why people make planetary posts to propitiate in almost every religions pagodas and temples. According to Buddhism, it is not necessary to build them.

Based on the Indian culture and astrology, Myanmar astrologers (scholars) created astrology and physiognomist and propitiation mainly, Sayadaw Khin Gyi Pyaw. He was so famous that almost, everybody had ever heard of him translated Myanmar astrology (Mach rote) into Myanmar version.

Therefore, Myanmar people are ones who accept other’s customs and slither not copying directly and just take out what should be needed, and we have recreated them in on ways of thinking.

Although Myanmar people partly accept that plants and spirits (Nat) can influence people’s fortune big the view of Hinduism, their belief in fortune in not without brain and they trust that they can change their fortune. With the help of astrology, we can predict own fortune and we can escape from our fate by during good deeds. Thus, we should try to smooth our future path breaking through our bad things we did in own past by replacing one’s merit.

Different Aspects of Philosopher on Astrology

1. According to Karl Popper, philosopher and scientist, under the criterion of falsifiability, firstly proposed that astrology is a pseudoscience. Popper regarded astrology as "pseudo-empirical" in that 'it appeals to observation and experiment,' but 'nevertheless does not come up to scientific standards'. In contrast to scientific disciplines, come up to scientific standards'. In contrast to scientific disciplines, astrology has not responded to falsification through experiment.
2. In contrast to Popper, the philosopher Thomas Kuhn argued that it was not lack of falsifiability that makes astrology unscientific, but rather that the process and concepts of astrology are non-empirical. Kuhn thought that, though astrologers had, historically, made predictions that categorically failed, this in itself does not make it unscientific, nor do attempts by astrologers to explain away failures by claiming that creating a horoscope is very difficult. Rather, in Kuhn's eyes, astrology is not science because it was always more akin to medieval medicine; they followed a sequence of rules and guidelines for a seemingly necessary field with known shortcomings, but they did not research because the fields are not amenable (agreeable; open to; willing) to research, and so "they had no puzzles to solve and therefore no science to practice". While an astronomer could correct for failure, an astrologer could not. An astrologer could only explain away failure but could not revise the astrological hypothesis in a meaningful way. As such, to Kuhn, even if the stars could influence the path of humans through life astrology is not scientific.
3. The philosopher, Paul Thagard asserts that astrology cannot be regarded as falsified in this sense until it has been replaced with a successor. In the case of predicting behaviour, psychology is the alternative. To Thagard a further criterion of demarcation of science from pseudoscience is that the state-of-the-art must progress and that the community of researchers should be attempting to compare the current theory to alternatives, and not be "selective in considering confirmations and disconfirmations".

Progress is defined here as explaining new phenomena and solving existing problems, yet astrology has failed to progress having only changed little.

Criticism of Astrology by the Theory of Truth in Philosophy

Most philosophers, such as analytic philosophers, pragmatic philosophers and logical positivists, claim that a major task of philosophy is to pursue the questions, "what is truth and what is reality? In philosophy, in order to determine the truth and reality, there are three theories of truth. They are,

1. The Correspondence Theory of Truth,
2. The Coherence Theory of Truth, and
3. The Pragmatic Theory of Truth.

The Correspondence Theory of Truth: According to this theory, a proposition is true if it "corresponds" with a fact, and it is false if it does not correspond. For example, if a statement says that it is raining, and if we look outside, we find that it is really raining then the statement is true. But, in the outside, the circumstance is not raining, or we find that the circumstance is fine then the statement is false. Thus, the criterion of truth and falsity is decided by its corresponding with the fact or situation. That theory is applied by the empiricists and natural scientists. The natural scientists test or verify the statement in experience or laboratory. If a theory or statement is verified by correspondence of the fact, it is accepted as true and if it can be verified in repetition or again and again till it gives the same result then it is regarded as law.

The Coherence Theory of Truth: This theory is based on the interdependence of a set of propositions on one another and the fact that one set of propositions makes another set true. This theory states the relationship of one proposition to another or to others. All these propositions "cohere," or hang or stick together. For example, to state that the proposition, "The sun will rise tomorrow" is true is dependent on other true propositions concerning the earth's rotation around the sun, the sun's heat and light, and many others. It is certainly true that many propositions are dependent on others for their truth at least to some extent. For example, in geometry, mathematics, or logic, one can derive theorems once certain axioms are assumed to be true, such as "the shortest distance between two points is a straight line." And in logic, everything we say is dependent on the principle of identity, that A is A or a thing is what it is. According to logical positivism, such statements are tautology.

The Pragmatic Theory of Truth: This theory is sometimes called the "truth is what works" theory. First, one has to ask what is meant by the word "work" when used in this context. It is perfectly understandable to describe a piece of machinery as "working," or even a plan, meaning that it was actually workable. 11

Another way of stating the pragmatic theory of truth is to say that if certain propositions yield good consequences or utility or psychological satisfaction or human beings, then they are workable and therefore true.

Analysis of astrology by philosophical criterion of truth

Astrology has to be examined whether it is reliable or what kind of truth it can give to us. It is obvious that it cannot be verified by the **correspondence theory of truth** because the most philosophers including Karl Popper name it "**pseudo-science**" due to its lack of falsification or verification on its bases of empirical premises.

It cannot be applicable by the norm of **coherence theory** because Edward W. James points out, "Astrology is irrational not because of the numerous problems with mechanisms and falsification due to experiments, but because an analysis of the astrological literature shows that it is infused with fallacious logic and poor reasoning Astrological writings we meet little appreciation of coherence, blatant insensitivity of evidence, no sense of a hierarchy of reasons....."

However, astrology can be accepted as truth by the pragmatic method because astrology gives the devotees a good satisfaction though the exact relation of position of planet and human's deeds what the

astrologer says are true though it is not say necessarily related or it may be co-accident. Whatever the result of astrology may be, people felt mental satisfaction by knowing the condition of luck in his life. That outcome of satisfaction is a kind of workability or utility in his life. Thus, by that criterion of mental satisfaction or utility or workability the belief in astrology is truth for him. But, that belief may be wrong for the unbelievers. According to the pragmatists, truth is relative and individual; it is not universal, and there is no absolute truth or objective truth in human affairs.

As astrology gives the people satisfaction, it has been continuously standing since B.C 200 to the present day how sciences and technologies have been advanced. It is natural that every man has strong desire to know their future happening. People want to know what will it be happened when his certain job is done. When a lot of money is invested in economic those people have more desire to know whether that business will be successful or not. Some people try different ways to predict or to focus their future work. They effort to get help from their traditional nats or will go to the astrologer. They do what the nat-medium says or astrologer says to avoid the failure or obstacles. Whether the nat helps or not, what the astrologer says will be true or not, the devotees get satisfaction by doing what the nat-medium or astrologer or other fortune-tellers say though they do not definitely know whether it will be secure or not. They get satisfaction because they have done what they ought to do to prevent the unlucky problems. When people get success it strengthens their belief more in astrology. But, if they do not get success or what the astrologer's predictions are missed, they blame themselves, but not to the astrology.

Thus, whether astrology is a pseudo-science or a pure science, or a kind of "state-of-the-art" as philosopher Paul Thagard asserted, it was believed in the past, it is believed at present and will be believed in the future so long as nature of human beings' has desire to know their future luck. It is natural that everybody has desire to know their future situation whether it is good or bad. People want to hear the sayings of astrologers, prediction of fortune-tellers about their future luck in whatever they do.

Conclusion

We have examined the nature of astrology from different versions and we find that it cannot be confirmed objectively as well as it cannot be denied. Will we accept it as pseudo-science as Karl Popper said?

However, in ethics especially in the Chinese, Hinduism, and other eastern ethics it is maintained that human beings' behaviours and the nature are mutually related. If the human beings' deeds are good, the weather is fine but if the men's deeds are evil, the weather will be bad. Besides, we find that the planet of earth and other planets are causally connected; for example, the gravitation of moon and sun determines the changes of tides and other weather conditions.

Thus, the scholars hold that the latest discovery in astrology can correlate the patterns of the solar system with the patterns of men' lives. There are patterns of potential in the revolution of each individual life circle and various stages of life are illuminated through the astrological use of progression and transits.

Again, as the paper has described in the content - - the European astrology also believes that the phenomena of the movement of the sun, moon, plant, stars can be powerful over human's fortune and can create the changes.

For example, (1) The meet of Jupiter and Saturn in a Zodiac determines people's fortune - - the US presidents who is elected in such year is elected in such year is assassinated or die in other ways ; (2) The meet of Jupiter and Saturn in Capricorn determined the death of the Us president William Harrison (3) The meet of Jupiter and Saturn in Virgo determined assassination of the US president Abraham Lincoln; (4) The meet of Jupiter and Saturn in

Virgo determined the assassinate of the Us president Kennedy; (5) the meet of Jupiter and Saturn in Virgo determined the assassinated of US president Reagan, etc...

From those above particular observe instances we can draw the general conclusion, "There is a determinism between positions of certain planets and certain person's fortune". Thus, we must accept the determinism of position and movement of planets and human being's actions though some philosopher hold the indeterminism and fatalism. This paper also holds, "There is universal causation both in nature and human's actions"; there cannot be effect without cause; though there are accidents and chances in nature and human's behaviours, those accidents and chances have certain cause to occur them.

Here, we must see the differentiation of physical nature and human nature in characters. Physical nature is changing in its spontaneous, physical process or unconscious process but human nature is in conscious process or teleological movement. It means that though there is determinism in human nature man has chances to choose to do; he can do his action with regard to what he ought to do. Thus, man has also freedom to change his life, and man can modify his deeds with a certain purpose within his determination. It means that human nature is in soft determinism.

With regard to that doctrine, there is an event to clarify that, once there is a reliable and trustworthy astrologer whose predictions are absolutely true. The, one day a stranger came to him to check his fortune. The astrologer checked his future again and again and found that the stranger would die within one week. Thus, the stranger went back to his home unhappily. But, in his way to his home he cleaned the road and supported the branches which bent down to the ground and blocked the road. In his home, he was waiting the day to die. One week had passed but he did not die; two weeks had passed but he did not die. When three weeks later, he went back to the astrologer and showed his health. When astrologer checked his fortune, it was found that the good deeds or good merits the stranger did in way to return saved his death. It shows that determinism can be reformed or modified by doing good deeds.

Another obvious event is about king *Azzardathard* who has been determined to suffer heavy and deep punishment due to his misdeed. But, by listening and practicing the teaching of the Lord Buddha, he regretted and did the good deeds heartily; thus, he had to suffer rather light punishment than before due to his good merits. That is the evidence of soft determinism in human nature.

The Theravada Buddhism holds the law of *kamma* which means that if a person does good deed he may enjoy good consequence, but if a person does the evil deed then he will suffer evil result. As you sow, so you will reap. The Buddhism has ways to mend the evil deeds by substituting good deeds.

By examining the role of astrology in human beings' actions, it is found that it is neither validated nor absolutely denied because it cannot account for the relation between the positions of the planets in heaven and the actions of human being in the earth planet. But there are events which occur under the influence of the position of the planets. But, those events may be co-accident. Thus, astrology cannot be verified in experience. It is beyond experience and metaphysical in nature. Men should not rely on it and its future prediction. Men should differentiate what is actual reality in present circumstances and what is only human's prediction about future. The study of the nature of astrology leads us to analyse the actuality of present and possibility of future prediction in social affairs.

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ဘုန်းကြည် (ပေါင်းတည်)၊ ၁၉၈၁ နက္ခတ်ကြည့်ရှုနည်းနှင့်ကြယ်ပုံပြင်များ၊ ဥဒြမြိုင်စာပေ၊ ရန်ကုန်မြို့။